

The Empirical Study of Effect Fairness, Disclosure and Transparency on Satisfaction at Royal Prima Hospital in Medan

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Abstract:- This research was conducted with the aim of analyzing the influence of GCG on patient satisfaction at Prima Medan Hospital. This research uses quantitative cross-sectional survey methods. Research object at Prima Medan Hospital. The research location is Prima Medan Hospital. The population of this study were all patients at Prima Medan Hospital. The data analysis technique uses univariate and bivariate analysis. The research results show that GCG influences patient satisfaction.

Keywords:- Fairness, Disclosure, Transparency, Patient Satisfaction And Hospitalization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Health is one of the rights of Indonesian citizens. The health sector is currently a very important topic. This relates to the impact of climate change on today's globalization. Existing industrial developments have a negative impact on the environment. Until now, companies in Indonesia continue to grow. The healthcare sector that is most affected by this critical situation must be ready to provide a health care platform that can adapt to the Covid-19 prevention protocol. In addition, good quality health services must also be in accordance with policies, standards, health and scientific evidence to achieve good results (Irvan, 2017).

Suryanto (2019) explains that GCG is a system for directing and controlling company activities, providing rights, obligations, directors, managers and interests in the organization's business in the organization's success in providing long-term profits and service quality. RSU Royal Prima Medan provides services to customers that are quite professional but supported by tools and equipment and a friendly environment.

There are widespread complaints about health services at RSU Royal Prima Medan. The researcher took the inpatient unit as the research location because the researcher had difficulty interviewing outpatients because the patients were not willing to take the time to be interviewed so that in the initial survey the researchers conducted interviews with inpatients, namely as many as 10 patients as respondents regarding the services provided by the RSU. Royal Prima Medan. Based on interview results, 60% of patients complained about the services provided by RSU Royal Prima Medan both doctors and nurses, information can be miss by health worker in service.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

➤ *Corporate Governance*

The term corporate governance refers to the influence between share holders, board of directors and top management in determining the direction and performance of a corporation. Hunger and Loheelen argue that the corporation is a mechanism built so that various parties can contribute capital, expertise, and labor for mutual benefit (Tjager, *et al*, 2003). At the end of the 1980s, many conclusions began to be drawn which stated that the ownership structure in the form of dispered ownership would have an impact on poor management performance.

Company management refers to the board of directors, shareholders, top management to improve performance. Hunger and Loheelen in Tjager, *et al*, (2003) explain capital, expertise and labor for mutual benefit. In 1980, a decision was made that the ownership structure would be in the form of ownership with its impact on management.

Corporate Governance often used as a term as it is originally in English, without translating it into Indonesian vocabulary. For various reasons, the exact equivalent word has not been found. According to the author, governance is the right term to Indonesian governance. In the term of governance, it contains the meaning of control and regulate so that it is able to explain the processes that occur therein. Ahmad Syakhroza in Wau (2021) provides an understanding of corporate governance as a comprehensive unit that includes cultural, legal and other institutional aspects in the form of mechanisms based on the concept of corporate control and an accountability system from those in control (Wau, 2021).

➤ *Patient Satisfaction*

Satisfaction was one indicator of the success of a service provider in providing services to customers (Kotler, 2009). Satisfaction " a measure of the extent to which patients feel satisfied with the health care they receive from health care providers (Manolitzas, 2016). Patient satisfaction is the level of satisfaction experienced by patients after using the service. Therefore, from the patient's point of view, it sometimes reflects a gap between the service expected and the experience of obtaining the service. Measuring patient satisfaction has become an integral part of hospital management strategies worldwide.

The quality of healthcare services and customer satisfaction are indicators of successful service delivery in hospitals. In addition, quality assurance and accreditation processes in most countries require that patient satisfaction be measured regularly (Suratri, 2018). By comparing between the patient's perception and the patient's expectations will bring up feelings of pleasure or satisfaction and disappointment or dissatisfaction. Customers or patients will feel satisfied if the patient's perceptions match their expectations, feel dissatisfied if the perceptions are smaller or do not match expectations and will cause feelings of great satisfaction if the results of the patient's perceptions are greater than their expectations (Kotler, 2009).

III. METHODS

This study used a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional survey design. In this study, researchers used questionnaires collected from respondents as a source of information to analyze the influence between the concept of Good Corporate Governance and patient satisfaction,

through approach, observation and data collection at one time. All patients who were hospitalized at the Royal Prima Medan General Hospital at the time the study was carried out constituted the population. The type of population to be studied is infinite population, because researchers do not know the exact number of inpatients at the Royal Prima Medan General Hospital during the study.

This research sample were 100 person. The independent variabel were Good Corporate Governance with the principles of fairness (X1), disclosure and transparency (X2), accountability (X3), and responsibility (X4). The dependent variable were patient satisfaction of RSU Royal Prima Medan. Analysis method were univariate and bivariate analysis

IV. RESULTS

➤ *The Relationship between Fairness and Patient Satisfaction*

The corelation of fairness on patient satisfaction can see this Table 1.

Table 1. The Corelation of Fairness on Patient Satisfaction

Fairness	Patient Satisfaction								p-value
	Not good		Pretty good		Very good		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Not good	35	35.0	2	2.0	3	3.0	40	40.0	0.000
Pretty good	3	3.0	28	28.0	8	8.0	39	39.0	
Very good	0	0	1	1.0	20	20.0	21	21.0	
Total	38	38.0	31	31.0	31	31.0	100	100	

Source: processed data

Based on table 1, it is known that of the 100 respondents studied, 40 (40.0%) respondents stated that fairness was not good. There were 35 (35.0%) respondents who stated that fairness was not good and patient satisfaction was not good, as many as 2 (2.0%) respondents stated that fairness was not good and patient satisfaction was quite good, and as many as 3 (3.0%) respondents who stated that fairness was not good and patient satisfaction was very good. There is an corelation of fairness on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan.

➤ *The Relationship of Transparency to Patient Satisfaction*

The corelation of transparency on patient satisfaction can be seen in table 2.

Table 2. The Corelation of Transparency on Patient Satisfaction

Transparency	Patient Satisfaction								p-value
	Not good		Pretty good		Very good		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Not good	36	36.0	1	1.0	6	6.0	43	43.0	0.000
Pretty good	2	32.0	28	28.0	7	7.0	37	37.0	
Very good	0	0	2	2.0	18	18.0	20	20.0	
Total	38	38.0	31	31.0	31	31.0	100	100	

Source: processed data

Based on Table 2, it is known that of the 100 respondents studied, 43 (43.0%) respondents stated that transparency was not good. There were 36 (36.0%) respondents who stated that transparency was not good and patient satisfaction was not good, as many as 1 (1.0%) respondents stated that transparency was not good and patient satisfaction was quite good, and as many as 6 (6.0%) respondents who stated that transparency is not good and patient satisfaction is very good. This was a corelation of transparency on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan.

➤ *The Relationship between Accountability and Patient Satisfaction*

The correlation of accountability on patient, can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Influence of Accountability on Patient Satisfaction

Transparency	Patient Satisfaction								p-value
	Not good		Pretty good		Very good		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Not good	36	36.0	1	1.0	6	6.0	43	43.0	0.000
Pretty good	2	320	28	28.0	7	7.0	37	37.0	
Very good	0	0	2	2.0	18	18.0	20	20.0	
Total	38	38.0	31	31.0	31	31.0	100	100	

Source: processed data

Based on table 3 it is known that of the 100 respondents studied, respondents who stated that transparency was not good were 43 (43.0%) respondents. There were 36 (36.0%) respondents who stated that transparency was not good and patient satisfaction was not good, as many as 1 (1.0%) respondents stated that transparency was not good and patient satisfaction was quite good, and as many as 6 (6.0%) respondents who stated that transparency is not good and patient satisfaction is very good. There is an correlation of transparency on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan.

➤ *The Relationship between Accountability and Patient Satisfaction*

The correlation of accountability on patient satisfaction seen in the table below:

Table 4. The Correlation of Accountability on Patient Satisfaction

Transparency (Disclosure and Transparency)	Patient Satisfaction								p-value
	Not good		Pretty good		Very good		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Not good	37	37.0	5	5.0	7	7.0	49	40.0	0.000
Pretty good	1	1.0	26	26.0	3	3.0	30	39.0	
Very good	0	0	0	0	21	21.0	21	21.0	
Total	38	38.0	31	31.0	31	31.0	100	100	

Source: processed data

Based on table 4, it is known that out of the 100 respondents studied, 49 (49.0%) respondents stated that accountability was not good. There were 37 (37.0%) respondents who stated that accountability was not good and patient satisfaction was not good, as many as 5 (5.0%) respondents stated that accountability was not good and patient satisfaction was quite good, and as many as 7 (7.0%) respondents stated that accountability was not good and patient satisfaction was very good. This result can be there is an correlation of accountability on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan.

➤ *The Relationship of Responsibility to Patient Satisfaction*

The correlation of responsibility (responsibility) on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan, can be seen in table 5.

Table 5. The Correlation of Responsibility on Patient Satisfaction

Responsibility	Patient Satisfaction								p-value
	Not good		Pretty good		Very good		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Not good	36	36.0	2	2.0	6	6.0	44	44.0	0.000
Pretty good	2	320	27	27.0	9	9.0	38	38.0	
Very good	0	0	2	2.0	16	16.0	18	18.0	
Total	38	38.0	31	31.0	31	31.0	100	100	

Based on table 5 it is known that out of the 100 respondents studied, 40 (40.0%) respondents stated that the responsibility was not good. There were 35 (31.5%) respondents who stated that the responsibility (responsibility) was not good and patient satisfaction was not good, as many as 2 (2.0%) respondents stated that the responsibility (responsibility) was not good and patient

satisfaction was quite good, and as many as 3 (3.0%) respondents who stated that the responsibility (responsibility) is not good and patient satisfaction is very good. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of responsibility (responsibility) on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan.

V. DISCUSSION

➤ *The Relationship between Fairness and Patient Satisfaction*

Based on the test results show that there is a relationship of fairness to patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan. The results showed that the aspect of fairness in patients saw that the hospital in carrying out service management had implemented division of tasks according to their respective professions and expertise without any discrimination and In this case, of course, there are standards that must be followed regarding the duties and functions of the institution, so that all can play a fair and functional role. An unfair task distribution system will certainly have an impact on the quality of service and the image of the hospital will be bad in the eyes of the public. The implementation of the tasks carried out must receive periodic evaluations of work results to prove success in carrying out their duties and functions and responsibilities.

This research is in line with research conducted by Annisah (2019) which found that fairness with the performance of non-medical patients at RSI Siti Khadijah Palembang can be caused because if fairness or fairness is applied in hospitals such as always being treated fairly, it does not discriminate when there is a promotion between patients. equal, non-subjective performance appraisal, and the elements of fairness in other Good Corporate Governance have been good, then the patient will be more enthusiastic and motivated to work well because they feel they are treated fairly and have appropriate rights and responsibilities so that the patient's performance can be to be better. Researchers assume that hospitals must have a complaint handling service to receive suggestions and criticisms as well as complaints from customers.

➤ *The Relationship between Transparency to Patient Satisfaction*

The test results show that there is a relationship transparency on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan. The results of research conducted at RSU Royal Prima regarding the implementation of GCG in the transparency aspect found that in practice the transparency aspect has been going well but there are certain things that are hospital privacy, so not everything is done transparently and only to certain parts and people. certain people who can find out, for example, the patient's disease. Officers are not transparent to patients but rather to the patient's family with several considerations

The results of study also found that management is responsible for patient health reports. Transparency can create good governance, so it must be able to provide information openly and as a whole to patients. Based on the research results, it can be seen that overall information transparency has been carried out, but there is some information that is not fit for public consumption. Provision of information openly must also be conveyed clearly, so that all staff and patients can understand it, as well as the user community. Good information management is a

manifestation of efforts to develop good and wise organizational management within an organization.

Based on the results of research on the transparency aspect in the roles, duties and responsibilities above, it can be seen that the director is very open in carrying out his role as a director, providing supervision, evaluating performance and providing managerial guidance in implementing good governance so that the hospital organization can run optimally. Transparency in the duties and responsibilities of each officer has been carried out properly in accordance with the main duties and functions of each. Transparency in carrying out activities in the management of good governance must be based on shared commitment. The transparency component must be carried out properly and comprehensively where the leadership provides oversight, direction, guidance and motivation in an open and truthful manner.

The results of study are in line with research conducted by Supriatini, et al (2019) who found that All principles and rules relating to compliance with hospital management rules have been regulated very clearly in hospital governance, especially regarding hospital transparency as a guideline for good hospital governance and as a form of implementation in improving and providing health services to achieve health goals. national

➤ *The Relationship between Accountability Against Patient Satisfaction*

Based on the test results, it was found that there was a relationship between accountability and patient satisfaction in. The results of research on legal accountability and health services can be seen that the implementation of legal accountability has been carried out well, because health service organizations are very committed to really being able to provide maximum service to patients. The provision of services is adjusted to the expertise of health professionals who have adapted to the needs and are supported by complete health facilities that can speed up the patient's healing process. The implementation of legal accountability is an aspect that must be carried out properly, acting in accordance with established service policies and procedures. Health professionals must uphold their respective health professional code of ethics.

Research results related to the implementation of financial accountability, carried out properly and correctly in accordance with standards and ministry regulations. The financial reporting system is authentic evidence that must be accounted for. This aims to be able to realize increased revenue and cost efficiency. The implementation of accountability in the HR sector has been carried out in its entirety considering that it has to adjust to the conditions of the stipulated budget, but the medical committee and the head of nursing stated that salaries have not been fully adjusted to the applicable employment minimum wage.

RSU Royal Prima in its accountability can be seen in the organizational structure which already has clear organizational structure sections and division of tasks and

functions that facilitate the operational activities of the hospital in providing health services. Accountability itself is the clarity of functions, implementation and accountability of the organization so that hospital management is carried out effectively. Each division has carried out its duties properly due to good coordination.

➤ *The Relationship between Responsibility Against Patient Satisfaction*

Based on the test results, it was explained that there was a relationship between responsibility and patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of the Royal Prima Medan Hospital. obtain protection of occupational safety and health, morals and decency, and treatment in accordance with human dignity and values and religious values. Any income received by individual or corporate taxpayers is subject to tax.

The results of research on the implementation of responsibility can be seen that RSU Royal Prima has implemented the principle of responsibility where the wage system has been adjusted to the regulations set by the ministry, but there are still patients who have the status of honorary workers. flat. Implementation of responsibility in hospital management standards, as medical committees and heads of nursing have been running according to nursing service standards, all nursing service procedures already have SOPs as guidelines for the implementation of nurses in providing health services, nurses work according to their roles and functions as a nursing profession with carrying out procedures according to nursing care and health workers, the monitoring system is implemented as an effort to minimize errors in service and maintain the stability of the quality of services provided.

The implementation of responsibility requires health workers to be able to provide more productive health services so that this gives satisfaction in health services. This consistent as Halawa et al (2022) which showed that GCG haad effect on patient satisfaction

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of study it can be concluded that 1) fairness correlated on patient satisfaction; 2) transparency correlate on patient satisfaction; 3) Accountability correlated on patient satisfaction and 4) Responsibility correlated on the level of patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSU Royal Prima Medan.

Suggestions that can be suggested include the Royal Prima Medan General Hospital needs to increase the value of independence by implementing division of tasks according to their respective professions and expertise so that when serving patients, officers can work according to their profession and expertise and Royal Prima Medan Hospital needs to increase transparency better especially in terms of decision making and information about patient treatment.

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